

VeriFish

The sustainability indicator framework to communicate responsible aquafood production and consumption patterns

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D3.9 – VeriFish dissemination events roadmap

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Disclaimer

VeriFish offers a framework of verifiable sustainability indicators for communications about sustainability based on FAIR data from EU- and global aquafoods repositories, brought together through the extraordinary collaboration of European-wide actors like NOFIMA, EUROFIR and Poseidon. Leveraging on this indicator, VeriFish designs, develops, and disseminates a number of media products to help citizens, seafood consumers and retailers, associations and policy makers make informed consumption choices.

Glossary of terms

Item	Description
ASC	Aquaculture Stewardship Council
CCMC	CEN-CENELEC Management Centre
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
CINEA	European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
CoP	Community of Practice
CWA	CEN Workshop Agreement
DG MARE	Directorate-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries
EAB	External Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
EFFAB	European Forum of Farm Animal Breeders
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
GRSF	Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries
HoReCa	Hotels, Restaurants and Catering
IFDC	International Food Data Conference
IJCKG	International Joint Conference on Knowledge Graphs
IPMA	Portuguese Institute for Sea and Atmosphere
MAC	Market Advisory Council
METROFOOD-EPI	METROFOOD Research Infrastructure – European Research Infrastructure Consortium Preparatory Phase / related stakeholder initiative
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
STECF	Scientific, Technical and Economic Committee for Fisheries

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable presents the dissemination events roadmap developed under VeriFish Task 3.5 and documents how event-based activities supported the project's communication, stakeholder engagement and outreach objectives throughout the project period (May 2024 to April 2026).

The report shows that events were used not only to increase visibility of VeriFish results, but also to create dialogue around the project's main outputs, including the indicator framework, communication guidelines, web app and media products. In particular the three-day final event combined a CWA workshop, a public dissemination and validation day, and a consortium meeting, allowing the project to connect external outreach with internal refinement and exploitation planning.

Across the project period, VeriFish was represented in a range of external events relevant to seafood sustainability, food systems, traceability, aquaculture, nutrition, policy and stakeholder dialogue. These activities helped position the project within broader European and international discussions, while also supporting networking and clustering with related initiatives. Their value was strongest where VeriFish was explicitly presented or discussed in relation to its outputs and target audiences.

Overall, the roadmap confirms that event-based dissemination made a relevant contribution to awareness raising, stakeholder engagement, validation of project outputs, and wider visibility of VeriFish in sectoral and policy environments. It also highlights lessons for future projects, particularly the need for strong evidence captures, careful wording, and a focus on event quality and follow-up.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose of Deliverable D3.9

Deliverable *D3.9 VeriFish dissemination events roadmap*, documents the event-based dissemination work carried out under the project and provides the formal record of the VeriFish conference as a core dissemination milestone. The deliverable contains a description of the VeriFish conference overall goal, the conference agenda, the list of participants, and a table summarising consortium participation in events during the project period.

The purpose of this deliverable is to show how events supported the communication and dissemination objectives of VeriFish by increasing visibility, creating opportunities for stakeholder exchange, validating project outputs, and positioning the project in broader European discussions on seafood sustainability communication.

1.2. Link to WP3 and Task T3.5: Events & VeriFish Conference

D3.9 is part of *Work Package 3: Communication outreach campaigns & prototype media products*, led by Eurofish with contributions from all VeriFish partners. WP3 was designed to raise awareness, inform and promote VeriFish assets among identified stakeholder groups, and increase consumer awareness of how to “choose fish” based on verifiable indicators. The work package combined communication campaigns, stakeholder engagement, media products, and outreach activities to make the project’s results accessible and useful for different audiences.

Within WP3, Deliverable D3.9 is directly linked to *Task 3.5 Events & VeriFish conference*, which run from month 3 to month 24 and is led by Eurofish with participation from all partners. This task aimed to maximise visibility and raise awareness of the project’s goals, vision, and actions through consortium participation in at least one event per partner, as well as through the organisation of a dedicated VeriFish conference bringing together industry experts, policymakers, consumer organisations and other relevant stakeholders. The task also included cooperation with like-minded EU projects and initiatives to ensure complementarity and avoid duplication.

The final event, held in Brussels on 10 –12 March 2026, combined three distinct but connected components: the CEN Workshop Agreement (CWA) final workshop on 10 March, the public final event on 11 March, and a consortium meeting on 12 March. This structure reflects the logic of Task 3.5 well: dissemination, stakeholder dialogue, validation, and internal consolidation were organised as parts of one coherent final event sequence.

1.3. Scope and methodology of the report

The report is based on documentary evidence produced during project implementation. The core sources used for the final event section are the official final event agenda, the final event minutes, moderation notes, presentation material, and participant/signature sheets for the Brussels meeting. These documents

provide evidence on the event structure, thematic sessions, chairs and speakers, validation workshops, discussion topics, and attendance across the three days. The event took place at Comet Louise in Brussels from 10 to 12 March 2026. The public part of the final event on 11 March had three plenary sessions, each dedicated to environmental, nutritional, or socio-economic indicators. This was followed by validation workshops and plenary wrap-up.

For the external events overview, the report relies on project records and supporting documentation compiled during WP3 implementation. Events are identified, classified, and summarised according to their relevance for dissemination, stakeholder engagement, validation, networking, or strategic positioning. Where relevant, the report distinguishes between project-organised events and external events attended by consortium partners.

2. Role of Events in the VeriFish dissemination strategy

Event-based dissemination in VeriFish was one of the core mechanisms for making project results visible, understandable, and usable. The project aimed to raise awareness, inform and promote VeriFish's main assets among identified stakeholder categories, while increasing consumers' awareness of how to "choose fish" based on verifiable indicators. This defines broader objectives that are directly relevant to events: translating the project's seafood and aquaculture indicators into accessible media products, building a community of practice around these outputs, promoting awareness through communication and dissemination campaigns, and engaging stakeholders at local and EU level through a coordinated strategy.

Within that logic, events had a very clear purpose: they maximise visibility and raise awareness of the project's goals, vision and actions. Consortium members were expected to promote VeriFish results and benefits through participation in events during the project period. It also established the dedicated VeriFish conference as the project's flagship event, bringing together industry experts, policymakers, consumer associations and other relevant stakeholders to present best practice recommendations and guidelines, share findings, promote dialogue, and explore innovative solutions for the use of verifiable indicators in seafood consumption. The objective was to use events as structured opportunities for dissemination, dialogue, validation and strategic positioning.

A further objective of event-based dissemination was to support complementarity with related European initiatives. Task 3.5 links VeriFish participation in events to cooperation with like-minded EU projects and initiatives aligned with the European Green Deal, the EU Mission Restore our Oceans and Waters by 2030, and the Farm to Fork strategy. VeriFish used events to situate them within wider debates on transparency, seafood communication, sustainability indicators and responsible consumption.

A primary function of events in VeriFish was visibility. WP3 and the project communication plan logic are built around targeted outreach, live dissemination channels, and the production of content that can circulate beyond the consortium.

Another key role of events was stakeholder engagement. VeriFish built a community of practice and involved stakeholders through coordinated communication activities: meetings, workshops, surveys and interviews involving internal and external stakeholders such as industry actors, retailers, regulatory bodies and policymakers.

Project-organised events, above all the VeriFish workshop and working lunch at the Catch Welfare Annual Conference and VeriFish final event allowed the project to present results in a coherent narrative, organise dialogue around its three main pillars, and run dedicated validation activities on VeriFish App, guidelines and media products. External events inserted VeriFish into existing professional, policy and public arenas where relevant audiences were already present.

3. Overview of the VeriFish Final Event

3.1. Event concept and strategic rationale

The VeriFish Final Event¹ was designed as the project's main closing dissemination milestone under Task 3.5 and was organised as a three-day sequence: Day 1 focused on the CWA and its dissemination follow-up, Day 2 on public dialogue and validation around the project's environmental, nutritional and socio-economic pillars, and Day 3 on the internal consolidation of outputs still under preparation.

This format first consolidated and discussed one of the project's core recommendation outputs, then presented the broader project results to external audiences and collected feedback and finally translated the outcomes into concrete follow-up actions for final deliverables and exploitation planning.

3.2. Dates, venue and format

The VeriFish Final Event took place from 10 to 12 March 2026 at Comet Louise, Place Stéphanie 20, 1050 Brussels, Belgium. The event was organised in a hybrid format, allowing both physical attendance in Brussels and remote participation, and was divided into the three consecutive components:

- Day 1 (10 March 2026): VeriFish CWA workshop
- Day 2 (11 March 2026): Public final event
- Day 3 (12 March 2026): Consortium meeting

The public event itself combined plenary sessions in the morning with two breakout validation workshops in the afternoon, followed by a plenary wrap-up and networking cocktail, which reinforced both the dissemination and interaction dimensions of the event.

¹ <https://verifish.info/verifish-final-event/>

Figure 1: VeriFish Final Event announcement

3.3. Main objectives of the final event

The first was to **present the main results of VeriFish in a coherent and accessible way**. Day 2 public programme was organised around the three core dimensions of the VeriFish framework: environmental sustainability, nutritional contribution, and socio-economic aspects of seafood systems, to present the project as an integrated approach to communicating seafood sustainability through verifiable indicators.

The second objective was **to create dialogue around those results**. For that, each thematic session during Day 2, included short pitches followed by moderated panel discussions involving actors from research, industry, governance, civil society and related initiatives.

The third objective was validation. The afternoon programme included a **VeriFish validation workshop** covering three project outputs: the web app, the guidelines for seafood value-chain actors, and the public engagement tools. Participants were asked to discuss usability, clarity, implementation barriers and missing messages, using both paper and online feedback.

A fourth objective was **consolidation and follow-up of VeriFish activities and results**. The consortium meeting that followed the public final event served to finalise linked outputs, including the CWA and its dissemination plan, and upcoming project deliverables.

4. Day 1: VeriFish CWA Workshop

4.1. Purpose and relation to project results

The first day of the VeriFish Final Event, held on 10 March 2026, was dedicated to the VeriFish CWA Workshop (<https://verifish.info/cen-workshop-agreement-cwa/>). The session ran from 13:00 to 17:00 CET at Comet Louise, Brussels, and was structured as a focused meeting around the draft CEN Workshop Agreement (CWA). 15 people attended physically and 11 online.

Figure 2: CEN Workshop Agreement presentation Event webpage

The purpose of this workshop was to review, discuss and consolidate the CWA as one of the project’s key recommendation-oriented outputs. The session was framed as a formal and content-driven meeting dealing with workshop procedures, the draft text, editorial changes, informal support for the document, and the dissemination and follow-up plan. The presentation of the workshop also explained why the CWA mattered: provide recommendations on how to efficiently communicate with consumers about seafood

and to engage and influence various types of consumers to encourage consumption of sustainable seafood.

4.2. Agenda and main discussion points

The official agenda for Day 1 included the following sequence: opening of the meeting and roll call, presentation of CEN Workshop content and formalities, overall presentation of the CWA draft, detailed presentation and discussion of the text, an informal indication of support, and a final summary with conclusions, dissemination planning and follow-up.

The workshop began with procedural clarification on the CEN Workshop process, including the role of the workshop chairperson, the submission of the approved CWA to CCMC², and the broader rationale for using this format. The core of the session focused on the draft CWA text itself. The discussion addressed the scope and framing of the document, including whether and how the objective of encouraging seafood consumption should be expressed, how “sustainable” should be treated in the wording, and how to avoid overclaiming in communication contexts where legal restrictions vary across countries.

Figure 3: Presentation of the CWA at VeriFish final event (10/03/2026)

Another discussion point concerned the role of artificial intelligence tools, including ChatGPT, in planning or supporting seafood marketing campaigns. The discussion did not conclude that AI should be relied upon

² CEN-CENELEC Management Centre (CCMC)

blindly but that the use would need revision, context awareness and compliance with applicable legislations.

The workshop also addressed the relation of the CWA to the broader VeriFish framework. The document should reflect how the project had evolved, including the role of the three pillars, the verifiability logic, and the added value of grounding recommendations in structured evidence rather than loose communication advice.

4.3. Main outcomes and follow-up actions

The main outcome of the workshop was the consolidation of the CWA text through discussion and editorial comment.

A second important outcome was the clarification of how the CWA should be positioned after publication. The reviewed document would be published and should serve as a reference for actors working in seafood marketing. Once available, it should be distributed to the Community of Practice and Horizon Europe projects (OCCAM, FishEUTrust and MrGoodFish) and initiatives (EFF-CoP, MeCCAM) that could provide future links or dissemination pathways. It should also be uploaded to Zenodo for long-lasting availability.

Figure 4: Presentation of the CWA during the VeriFish Final Event (10/03/2026)

The workshop created a final scrutiny point for one of the Key Exploitable Result of the project, exposed the legal and practical limits of communication guidance, and set a dissemination path for the CWA beyond the formal life of the project.

Day 1 brought together a mixed group of consortium representatives and invited external experts or stakeholders relevant to the CWA discussion. The participant list includes representatives from Eurofish, Trust-IT, Nofima, EuroFIR, PMT, Clupea, Poseidon, IPMA, FAO, ASC, Ecsite, WRG Europe, Oceana, the Xunta de Galicia, the Delegation of the Balearic Islands and others. This profile fits the purpose of the day: a focused working session around the CWA draft and its positioning.

5. Day 2: Public Final Event

5.1. Event structure and thematic focus

The public final event took place on 11 March 2026 as the central of the three-day VeriFish final event sequence. It was co-organised with the FISHEUtrust Horizon Europe project and ran from 09:00 to 17:30 CET at Comet Louise, followed by a networking cocktail, and was organised in a hybrid format with on-site participation (47 participants) and Zoom access for remote attendees (41 attendees). The structure combined a morning plenary programme with thematic sessions and panels, followed by afternoon breakout and validation workshops.

The participant list includes consortium partners, representatives of EU and international organisations, research bodies, advisory and certification organisations, NGOs, communication actors, and other external participants. Organisations represented included CINEA, FAO, ASC, IPMA, Jožef Stefan Institute, FishTales, MAC, WRG Europe, Ecsite, EFFAB, Belit, DTU, Oceana, University of Florence, University of Medicine and Pharmacy Iuliu Hațieganu Cluj-Napoca, AquaBioTech Group, and others, alongside VeriFish partners.

The thematic logic of the day was tightly aligned with the architecture of the VeriFish framework. The morning sessions were built around the project's three core dimensions: environmental sustainability, nutritional contribution, and the socio-economic side of seafood systems. This reflected the project's central claim that seafood sustainability communication should not rely on a single metric or simplified label but should instead integrate multiple dimensions through verifiable indicators.

The collaboration with the FishEUtrust project broadened the discussion beyond the boundaries of VeriFish and positioned the event within a wider ecosystem of EU projects and initiatives dealing with seafood transparency, traceability, consumer engagement and sustainability communication.

5.2. Plenary sessions

The morning plenary started with the opening by Vicente Fernandez, DG MARE, European Commission, who made an overview of the policy context of the project, about the EU Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters and introduced some future and ongoing initiatives to which the project can create some synergies. The opening was followed by an introductory session where Sara Pittonet, Trust-IT Services, VeriFish coordinator, & Nives Ogrinc, Jožef Stefan Institute, FishEUtrust coordinator, framed the event introduction around the question *"What makes seafood truly sustainable?"*. This opening positioned seafood as a domain marked by information asymmetry, proliferation of labels and claims, oversimplification and loss of trust, while arguing for more transparent and structured communication through indicators and layered information tools.

5.2.1. Session 1: Environmental Sustainability of seafood and aquaculture

The first plenary session addressed Environmental Sustainability of seafood and aquaculture. The session combined short pitches from VeriFish (Ixai Salvo, Eurofish International Organisation) and FishEUTrust (Natalie Rizzo, DTU) representatives with a panel discussion moderated by Michelle Boonstra, Clupea, involving Ixai Salvo (Eurofish), Natalie Rizzo (DTU), Alessandro Manghisi (ASC), Anne Marie Cooper (ICES) and Carlos Mendoza (SmartWater Planet). The core message of the VeriFish contribution was that environmental sustainability in seafood is multi-dimensional and cannot be reduced to a single aggregated score. Instead, the project emphasised structured transparency, distance-to-target scoring, descriptive indicators, and the use of accessible tools such as QR-linked digital content.

Figure 5: Panel discussion during session 1 (VeriFish Final Event: 11/03/2026)

5.2.2. Session 2: What does seafood bring to our diets?

The second session focused on nutrition. This session brought nutritional indicators into the sustainability discussion and challenged the common reduction of food sustainability debates to environmental metrics alone. The presentation by Sian Astley (EuroFIR) stressed that seafood contributes important nutrients

such as omega-3 fatty acids, iodine, vitamin D, selenium and high-quality protein, and argued that without integrating nutritional value it is difficult to assess the role of seafood in sustainable diets. Too many sustainability debates confuse “lower impact” with “better food” and stop thinking there. The panel discussion moderated by Paul Finglas (EuroFIR), and the panellist were Anton Ellenbroek (FAO Consultant), Stephanos Cherouvis (Ecsite), Narcisa Bandara (IPMA) and Sian Astley (EUROFIR).

Figure 6: Presentation of Session 2 by EuroFIR (VeriFish Final Event 11/03/2026)

5.2.3. Session 3: Understanding the human side of seafood

The third session dealt with the human side of seafood, focusing on socio-economic indicators. The VeriFish contribution by Tracy Murai (Poseidon) presented a framework organised around governance, labour practices and rights, worker health and safety, and discrimination and Indigenous peoples, with indicators intended to capture contextual conditions and risk environments rather than make simplistic judgements about individual operators. The session was paired with a FishEUTrust contribution by Matteo Masotti (University of Bologna) on consumer trust in aquaculture, which introduced findings on consumer heterogeneity, barriers to consumption, and the limited effect of certification and traceability claims when compared with branding, familiarity and sensory preferences. The panel discussion moderated by Graeme Macfadyen (Poseidon), and the panellist were Irene Kranendonk (FishTales), Petter Olsen (Nofima), Marine Cusa (Oceana), Tracy Murai (Poseidon) and Matteo Masotti (University of Bologna).

Together, these plenary sessions gave the event conceptual breadth and prevented it from collapsing into a single-domain conversation.

5.3. Breakout and validation workshops

The afternoon part of Day 2 shifted from presentation to interaction, with two parallel breakout tracks running from 14:30 to 17:00, followed by a plenary wrap-up. One of these was the VeriFish Validation Workshop, replicated in two rounds so to allow all participants to join, which was explicitly designed as a structured feedback session on three project outputs: **the VeriFish web app, the guidelines for seafood value-chain actors, and the media/public engagement tools**. Participants were organised into small groups invited to nominate a scribe and provide group inputs via Slido.

Figure 7: Working group during breakthrough sessions (VeriFish Final Event 11/03/2026)

For the web app, participants were asked whether the tool was intuitive, whether the sustainability indicators were clear and understandable, and what information or functionality was missing. For the guidelines, they were asked whether value-chain actors could realistically apply them in practice, whether the indicators were clearly explained, and what barriers might prevent implementation. For the media tools, the questions focused on accessibility for non-experts, relative engagement potential, and missing messages about seafood sustainability.

The breakout design turned the public day into a final-stage testing environment for user-oriented outputs developed under WP3 and linked WPs, exposing its outputs to external feedback and assessment before closure.

5.4. Main outcomes and feedback relevance for the project

The immediate outcomes of Day 2 were the public presentation of VeriFish results in a structured, stakeholder-facing format and second, the collection of targeted feedback that could still influence final refinements. The event presented the three VeriFish pillars, connected them with external perspectives, and made space for discussion across research, policy, industry and civil-society actors.

The relevance of this feedback for the project is straightforward. It strengthened the final stage of output refinement, provided external validation evidence for tools and guidance materials, and helped connect dissemination with exploitation and usability.

Figure 8: Group photo during VeriFish Final Event (11/03/2026)

6. Day 3: Consortium Meeting

Day 3 was an internal consortium meeting focused on the finalisation of remaining project deliverables and next steps after the public event. Discussions addressed outstanding work on key outputs, including recommendations, exploitation planning, the web app, and the communication report. The meeting

served to review progress, assign follow-up actions, and connect feedback from the previous days with the final refinement of project results.

The meeting was used to review the status of these outputs, identify outstanding needs, and agree on the next steps for completion. The minutes show that discussions covered further input to the EAB recommendations, exploitation planning and ownership of key results, refinements to the web app, and the preparation of the communication report structure. Several concrete actions were assigned, including additional feedback collection, adjustments to the app, clarification of exploitation elements, and preparation of the table of contents for D3.6. Overall, Day 3 served as an internal follow-up session linking the outcomes of the final event to the finalisation of project deliverables and post-project planning.

7. Participants in the VeriFish Final Event

7.1. Participants by organisation type and stakeholder category

The final event brought together a broad range of organisation types, which is consistent with the ambition of VeriFish to engage multiple stakeholder groups. Based on the participant lists and agenda materials, attendees can be grouped into several broad categories.

Project consortium and affiliated project partners, including Eurofish, Trust-IT, COMMpla, EuroFIR, Nofima, PMT, Clupea, Poseidon and FORTH. These participants were present across the event and were central to the delivery of presentations, moderation, technical discussion and follow-up planning.

Academic organisations, including DTU, Jožef Stefan Institute, IPMA, University of Florence, University of Medicine and Pharmacy Iuliu Hațieganu Cluj-Napoca, and others. These actors contributed scientific, technical and applied perspectives, particularly in the plenary sessions and panel discussions.

Policy, advisory and public-interest organisations, such as CINEA, FAO, MAC, the Xunta de Galicia and the Delegation of the Balearic Islands. Their presence is relevant because VeriFish is partly about how evidence and indicators travel into governance, advisory use and communication practice.

Industry, certification and value-chain related actors, such as ASC, Sustainable Fisheries Partnership, WRG Europe, FishTales, EFFAB and Belit. These organisations sit closer to the real-world application of communication tools, traceability approaches, market messaging and product-facing information systems.

Civil society, NGO and communication/intermediary actors, including Oceana, AquaBioTech Group and Ecsite, as well as participants involved in outreach and public engagement. Their presence reinforced the event's broader dialogue dimension.

The strength of the participant profile lies in a relevant cross-section of expert, advisory, applied and governance actors capable of discussing and testing VeriFish outputs in a meaningful way.

8. Consortium Participation in External Events During the Project Period

8.1. Approach to compiling the event record

An event record was set-up from the very beginning of the project tracking participation of consortium partners to third party events, an event was included only where VeriFish was explicitly presented, promoted, discussed as a project, or represented through identifiable dissemination activity. The event record distinguishes between different types of participation, including a keynote or formal presentation, presence on fairs; validation workshops and presentations

8.2. Summary table of consortium participation in external events

The table below summarises the external events identified across the project period, based on the event list provided and filtered according to the approach described above.

Table 1: Summary of external events attended by VeriFish

year	Event	Location	Main partner(s) involved	Type of participation
Jun/24	Tromsø Seafood Festival	Tromsø, Norway	Nofima	Public engagement
Jun/24	Visit of the Deputy Ambassador of Spain to Eurofish HQ	Copenhagen, Denmark	Eurofish	Bilateral institutional engagement
Sept/24	Eurofish Conference on Circular Economy in Seafood	Madrid, Spain	Eurofish	Conference / dissemination
Sept/24	AQUA 2024	Copenhagen, Denmark	Eurofish	Exhibition / networking / communication campaign
Sept/24	PolFish 2024	Gdańsk, Poland	Eurofish	Exhibition / networking
Oct/24	Conxemar 2024	Vigo, Spain	Eurofish	Trade fair / networking
Dec/24	METROFOOD-EPI Stakeholder Workshop / Open Event	Rome, Italy	EuroFIR	Stakeholder workshop
Dec/24	METROFOOD-EPI Open Event / Stakeholder Engagement	Rome, Italy	Trust-IT /EuroFIR	Open event / stakeholder engagement
Feb/25	Nofima-led Workshop on Consumer Communication	Tromsø, Norway	Nofima	Expert workshop
Feb/25	Mr.GoodFish 3.0 Co-Creation Workshop	Tromsø, Norway	Nofima	Co-creation workshop / presentation
Mar/25	European Ocean Days / Mission Ocean Forum 2025	Brussels, Belgium	Trust-IT / consortium representatives	Policy / clustering / outreach
Mar/25	Seafood Traceability Seminar / Sjókovin 5-Year Anniversary	Klaksvík, Faroe Islands	Nofima	Seminar / traceability discussion
Apr/25	EuroFIR AISBL FoodForum 2025	Brussels, Belgium	EuroFIR	Scientific / specialist forum

year	Event	Location	Main partner(s) involved	Type of participation
Apr/25	Seafood Expo Global 2025	Barcelona, Spain	Eurofish / Poseidon	Trade fair / dissemination / networking
May/25	Market Seminar on Fisheries and Aquaculture	Vilnius, Lithuania	Eurofish	Seminar / presentation
Jun/25	Eurofish Conference on Predators and Invasive Species	Tallinn, Estonia	Eurofish	Conference / dissemination
Jun/25	A Seat at the Table – Connecting Food, Culture, and Sustainability	Copenhagen, Denmark	Eurofish	Conference / public discussion
Aug/25	23rd International Congress of Nutrition (ICN 2025)	Paris, France	EuroFIR	Scientific congress
Sept/25	Aquaculture Europe 2025	Valencia, Spain	Eurofish / Trust-IT / NOFIMA	Fair / networking / dissemination
Sept/25	14th International Food Data Conference (IFDC 2025)	Rome, Italy	EuroFIR	Specialist scientific conference
Oct/25	Conxemar 2025	Vigo, Spain	Eurofish	Trade fair / dissemination / networking
Oct/25	14th International Joint Conference on Knowledge Graphs (IJCKG 2025)	Heraklion, Greece	FORTH / COMMpla	Scientific conference
Nov/25	Catch Welfare Platform Conference	Hybrid	Clupea / Trust-IT/ All partners	Conference / Working lunch / sector discussion
Jan/26	Arctic Frontiers 2026	Tromsø, Norway	Nofima	Conference / outreach
Feb/26	Market Advisory Council WG1 Meeting	Ostend, Belgium	Trust-IT / Clupea	Stakeholder / market advisory meeting
Feb/26	AquaFarm 2026	Pordenone, Italy	Eurofish / Trust-IT	Trade event / workshop / dissemination
Mar/26	Mission Ocean Forum 2026 / European Ocean Days	Brussels, Belgium	Trust-IT / Clupea	Policy / clustering / dissemination
Mar/26	Food 2030 Clustering Workshop: Food from the Ocean and Freshwater Resources	Brussels, Belgium	EuroFIR	Clustering workshop
Mar/26	OSCARs General Assembly	Seville, Spain	FORTH / Trust-IT	Open science / FAIR data event
Apr/26	Seafood Expo Global 2026	Barcelona, Spain	Eurofish / Poseidon	Trade fair / dissemination / networking

8.3. Type of participation: attendance, speaking roles, workshops, dissemination actions

The external event record shows that VeriFish participation covered several different modes of engagement, each with different dissemination value.

Formal presentation or speaking roles. Explicit, attributable presentation of project content. Examples include the Market Seminar on Fisheries and Aquaculture in Vilnius in May 2025, where Eurofish presented the VeriFish indicator framework, the Mr.GoodFish 3.0 Co-Creation Workshop where Nofima presented VeriFish indicators, and likely the more technical events involving EuroFIR or FORTH where specific project methods, datasets or infrastructure-related work were presented.

Figure 9: Mr.GoodFish 3.0 Co-creation workshop (February 2025 – Tromsø, Norway)³

Workshops, co-creation sessions and stakeholder engagement activities. These include events such as the METROFOOD-EPI stakeholder exchange, the Mr.GoodFish 3.0 workshop, the UNOC3 virtual side event, and the Market Advisory Council WG1 meeting.

Trade fairs and exhibitions, such as Seafood Expo Global, Conxemar, AquaFarm, and Aquaculture Europe. These events put VeriFish into contact with seafood-sector professionals, businesses, associations and market actors. Fairs are strategic for dissemination, stakeholder exchange, networking, visibility, project promotion, or stand-based materials where applicable

³ <https://verifish.info/collaborative-innovation-verifish-at-the-mr-goodfish-3-0-co-creation-workshop-in-tromso/>

Figure 8: Stakeholder working lunch and workshop. Catch Welfare Conference (19-21 November, 2025. IJmuiden, The Netherlands)

Policy, clustering and institutional engagement events, such as European Ocean Days / Mission Ocean Forum, the Food 2030 clustering workshop, and Brussels-based stakeholder meetings. These events are strategically important because they connect VeriFish to the wider Horizon Europe, Mission Ocean and policy ecosystem.

Scientific and specialist conferences, including events such as FoodForum 2025, ICN 2025, IFDC 2025, and IJCKG 2025. These are relevant where VeriFish methods, data structures, knowledge-base work, nutritional pillar, or evidence framework were explicitly presented.

Overall, the participation profile shows a mix of:

- simple attendance and networking
- explicit project presentations
- workshop and co-creation engagement
- dissemination through materials and fair presence
- clustering and policy dialogue
- scientific and technical positioning

8.4. Strategic relevance of the events attended

The strategic relevance of the external events attended can be understood through four main functions.

Sector visibility. Trade fairs and industry-facing conferences such as Catch Welfare Conference, Conxemar, Seafood Expo Global and Aquaculture Europe gave VeriFish access to professional seafood audiences. These are the places where producers, processors, market actors and sector organisations circulate.

Stakeholder testing and narrative refinement. Workshops and stakeholder events such as the Mr.GoodFish 3.0 co-creation session, MAC WG1, and the UNOC3 side event were strategically valuable because they exposed VeriFish ideas to questioning and comparison.

Scientific and methodological credibility. Events linked to EuroFIR, FORTH or technical communities were relevant because they helped position the project's data sources, integration logic, nutritional approach and knowledge-base infrastructure within specialised expert networks.

Policy and clustering relevance. Participation in Mission Ocean, Food 2030 and related EU clustering or Brussels-based engagements helped position VeriFish within the ecosystem of initiatives concerned with ocean governance, sustainable food systems, transparency and blue economy policy.

9. Assessment of Dissemination Value

9.1. Contribution to awareness raising

The event-based dissemination activities of VeriFish contributed to raising awareness of the project and its main outputs among relevant stakeholder groups throughout the project period. Through participation in conferences, fairs, workshops, clustering activities and policy-related events, VeriFish increased the visibility of its indicator framework, communication approach, web app, guidelines and media products in professional, scientific and institutional contexts.

The public final event in Brussels further supported this awareness-raising function by bringing together the environmental, nutritional and socio-economic pillars of VeriFish in one programme, alongside the app, guidelines and media outputs. This helped present the project's integrated approach to seafood communication and sustainability indicators across the different dimensions addressed by VeriFish.

9.2. Contribution to validation and feedback collection

Events contributed to the validation of VeriFish outputs and to the collection of stakeholder feedback throughout the project period. This was particularly evident in activities involving co-creation, specialised stakeholder exchange, expert presentations, and the final event in Brussels.

The final event included dedicated validation sessions on the web app, the guidelines and the media tools, with feedback focusing on usability, clarity, applicability and missing elements. The subsequent consortium meeting linked this input to follow-up actions on the app, recommendations, reporting and exploitation planning. In addition, external events such as co-creation workshops, scientific exchanges and stakeholder meetings provided opportunities to present project elements, discuss approaches and

gather reactions from relevant audiences. Overall, the event programme supported the refinement of project outputs through direct interaction with stakeholders and expert communities.

9.3. Contribution to networking, collaboration and policy visibility

The event programme contributed to expanding the project's network and increasing its visibility across sectoral, scientific and policy-related environments. Through participation in conferences, fairs, stakeholder meetings, workshops and clustering activities, VeriFish engaged with actors from research, industry, public institutions, advisory bodies, NGOs and related EU initiatives.

Several events supported collaboration and exchange with projects and organisations working on connected topics, particularly in the areas of seafood communication, transparency, traceability and sustainability. The final event in Brussels was one of the main moments for this, bringing together project partners, external stakeholders and related initiatives. The Catch Welfare Platform Conference was also an important event for stakeholder involvement, as it created an additional space for exchange with specialised actors and contributed to linking VeriFish-related work with broader discussions on welfare and seafood communication.

The events also increased the visibility of VeriFish in policy and stakeholder environments, including Mission Ocean activities, market and advisory meetings, and other EU-related forums. Overall, they supported the positioning of the project within wider discussions relevant to seafood sustainability, communication and responsible consumption.

10. Lessons Learned and Conclusions

The dissemination and outreach activities carried out under VeriFish show that events were used as an integral part of the project's communication and stakeholder engagement strategy. Under WP3 and Task 3.5, the project combined participation in external conferences, fairs, workshops, stakeholder meetings and policy-related events with the organisation of the final event in Brussels. Together, these activities supported the visibility of VeriFish in relevant sectoral, scientific and institutional environments and created opportunities to present, discuss and further refine the project's main outputs.

A key strength of the event strategy was the combination of dissemination, exchange and validation. This was particularly evident in the final event structure, which linked the CWA workshop, the public event and the consortium meeting in a coherent sequence. This format connected external communication with stakeholder feedback and internal follow-up on deliverables and exploitation. The public programme also reflected the core structure of VeriFish by presenting the environmental, nutritional and socio-economic dimensions together, alongside the app, guidelines and media outputs.

Another positive result was the ability of the event roadmap to reach a varied set of audiences. Across the final event and the wider external event programme, VeriFish engaged consortium partners, researchers,

advisory bodies, certification actors, NGOs, public institutions, market stakeholders and related EU initiatives. This supported the project's positioning within wider discussions on seafood sustainability, transparency, communication and responsible consumption. The participation in targeted external events, including stakeholder workshops, Mission Ocean activities, sector seminars and specialist forums, also helped extend the project's outreach beyond its own channels.

Overall, the event roadmap confirms that VeriFish used dissemination activities to strengthen awareness of the project, support stakeholder engagement, collect feedback on key outputs and increase its visibility within relevant professional and policy-related contexts. The final event in Brussels played a central role in this process, while the broader external event participation helped maintain the project's presence across the wider seafood, research and policy landscape.

11. Annexes

11.1. Annex I – Final Event Agenda

DAY 1 - CWA 10.03.2026 - 13:00 - 17:00 CET

Where: Comet Louise | Pl. Stéphanie 20, 1050 Bruxelles, Belgium

Chair: Petter Olsen, Nofima

Time	What
13.00	Opening of the meeting, Roll call of participants, Adoption of the agenda
13.15	CEN Workshop content and formalities
13.30	Overall presentation of the CWA draft
13.45	Detailed presentation, discussions, and editorial changes
14.45	Coffee break
15.15	Detailed presentation, discussions, and editorial changes
16.30	Who supports this CWA, informal voting
16.40	Summary, conclusions, plan for dissemination and follow-up
17.00	Meeting end

DAY 2 - Public Final event 11/03/2026 - 09:00 - 17:00 CET

Time	MORNING PLENARY SESSION
08:30 - 09:00	Registration & welcome coffee
09:00 -09:10	EC Opening
09:10 - 09:30	What makes seafood truly sustainable? VeriFish & FishEUTrust opening - Sara Pittonet, Trust-IT Services, VeriFish coordinator, & Nives Ogrinc, Jožef Stefan Institute, FishEUTrust coordinator
Session 1: Environmental Sustainability of seafood and aquaculture	
09:30 - 10:30	5 min Pitch from VeriFish - Ixai Salvo, Eurofish International Organisation 5 min Pitch from FishEUTrust - Natalie Rizzo - DTU Panel <i>Moderated panel discussion around environmental indicators</i> Chair: Michelle Boonstra, Clupea Pannellists: Alessandro Manghisi, ASC

	Anne Marie Cooper, ICES (online) Carlos Mandoza, SmartWater planet (online) Ixai Salvo, Eurofish International Organisation Natalie Rizzo, DTU 10 min Q/A from audience	
10:30 - 11:00	<i>Coffee break</i>	
	Session 2: What does seafood bring to our diets?	
11:00 - 12:00	5 min Pitch from EUROFIR / FishEUTrust - Sian Astley, EUROFIR Panel <i>Moderated panel discussion around nutritional indicators</i> Chair: Paul Finglas , EUROFIR Pannellists: Anton Ellenbroek, FAO Consultant Stephanos Cherouvis - Ecsite Narcisa Bandara, IPMA 10 min Q/A from audience	
	Session 3: Understanding the human side of seafood	
12:00 - 13.00	5 min Pitch from VeriFish - Tracy Murai, Poseidon Panel <i>Moderated panel discussion around socio-economic indicators</i> Chair: Graeme Macfadyen, Poseidon Pannellists: Irene Kranendonk, FishTales Petter Olsen, Nofima Marine Cusa, Oceana 10 min Q/A from audience	
13.00 14.30	<i>Sustainable Lunch</i>	
	AFTERNOON: BREAKOUT SESSIONS	
Time	BREAKOUT 1	BREAKOUT 2
14.30 - 15.30	VERIFISH VALIDATION WORKSHOP	FISHEUTRUST PLATFORM VALIDATION WORKSHOP
15:30 - 16:00	<i>Coffee break</i>	
16:00 - 17:00	FISHEUTRUST PLATFORM VALIDATION WORKSHOP	VERIFISH VALIDATION WORKSHOP
17:00 - 17:30	Plenary wrap-up from the day Sara Pittonet & Nives Ogrinc	
17:30 - 18:30	<i>Goodbye Cocktail</i>	

DAY 3 - Consortium meeting 12.03.2026 - 09:00 - 17:00 CET

Time	What
09.00 - 10.30	Upcoming deliverables
09.00 - 09:45	D1.6 Recommendations from VeriFish EAB on the way forward
09:45 - 10:30	D1.5 Impact monitoring and Exploitation of the project results
10:30 - 11:00	<i>Coffee break</i>
11.00 - 12.30	
11:00- 11:30	Calendar, puzzle & remaining media products
11:30 - 12:00	D3.5 Prototype of the web app - final release
12:00 - 12:30	D3.6 Communication, stakeholder engagement final report
12.30 - 14.00	<i>Lunch</i>